

HISTO-MRI Project

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D1.2: Gender Action Plan

Version	Date	Reviewer
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1 Deliverable description

This deliverable includes an analysis of the gender distribution within the consortium and a list of actions to be implemented to improve gender equality.

This deliverable is the result of *Task 4 Gender Action plan*, part of **WP1 – Management**.

2 Introduction

According to **Article 33.1 Obligation to aim for gender equality** of the Grant Agreement:

“The beneficiaries must take all measures to promote equal opportunities between men and women in the implementation of the action. They must aim, to the extent possible, for a gender balance at all levels of personnel assigned to the action, including at supervisory and managerial level.”

This article meets the objectives described in the **“Guidance on Gender Equality in Horizon 2020”**:

Three objectives underpin the Commission’s activities on gender equality in Horizon 2020. They are in line with RTD strategy on gender as well as with the ones set in the ERA Communication of July 2012:

- *Fostering gender balance in Horizon 2020 research teams, in order to address the gaps in the participation of women in the Framework Programme’s projects*
- *Ensuring gender balance in decision-making, in order to reach the Commission’s target of 40% of the under-represented sex in panels and groups (50% for Advisory Groups)*
- *Integrating gender/sex analysis in research and innovation (R&I) content, which helps improve the scientific quality and societal relevance of the produced knowledge, technology and/or innovation.*

These objectives are integrated in the Commission provisions for the implementation of Horizon 2020, at each stage of the research and innovation cycle.

The HISTO-MRI consortium is fully committed with these objectives and with the Article 33.1 of the Grant Agreement. This document describes the current status of gender balance in the consortium, the gender guidelines already implemented in the partners and some actions to promote gender equality in the project.

3 Current status

3.1.1 Statistics

The coordinator of the HISTO-MRI project has contacted the partners to compile the statistics of manpower and gender distribution of the personnel working in the project.

The results are reflected in the following table:

Partner	Total number of participants	Total number of women
CSIC	3	0
DANFYSIK	3	0
LUMC	2	0
FRAUNHOFER	2	0
TESORO	2	1
TOTAL	12	1

The analysis shows that only an 8% of the personnel working in the project are women. This is a very unbalanced situation and corrective actions are needed.

3.1.2 Existing gender action plans

One important part of the analysis is the existence of gender equality plans in the different partners. The coordinator has contacted all participants in the project in order to analyse this.

CSIC:

The document related to gender aspects at CSIC is the **II Plan for equality between men and women**. It was released on December 2015. As part of the Spanish Public Administration, it follows the **II Plan for Equality between women and men in the General State Administration and in its public bodies** approved by the Spanish Government. The plan for CSIC has as its main objectives:

- Establish and develop policies that integrate equal treatment and opportunities between women and men, without discrimination directly or indirectly by reason of sex.
- Promote measures to achieve real equality within the organization, establishing equal opportunities for women and men as a principle of our institutional policy.

With respect to the personnel selection processes, the criteria followed by CSIC are very strict. The process has to be open and transparent. The evaluation of the candidates is based only in the merites of the candidates (years of experience, publications, degrees, ...). This guarantees that no discrimination for sex reasons can exist.

Additionally, one of the actions in the plan of CSIC is the gender balance in the selection bodies and raising awareness in the culture of equality of the people who are members of the selection bodies to avoid unintended biases in merit evaluation.

As part of the Plan for equality, CSIC has other action lines:

- Training in equality between men and women
- Organization of working time, co-responsibility and conciliation measures of personal, family and work life

DANFYSIK:

This organization has no specific plans related to gender issues, but they follow gender equality criteria as part of their company philosophy.

LUMC:

As an organisation with more than 7000 employees, the LUMC wants to be sure it reflects our society. Inevitably this means paying attention to the right age distribution, accessibility irrespective of ethnicity or sexual preference, an adequate representation of women in managerial positions and removing obstacles to the participation of people with a work-limiting disability or those who are distanced from the labour market.

FRAUNHOFER:

The Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft aims to be a leading organization in realizing equal opportunities and the compatibility of job, family and leisure time. This corporate objective demands a strong commitment from the Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft in its internal and external relations. This can only be achieved through a greater willingness on the part of management.

Involving more women in applied research is an important objective of the Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft. Women's participation has to be increased in all areas where their participation is currently low.

Nevertheless, the goal of achieving a well-balanced gender distribution in the working environment has yet to be achieved. In terms of gender mainstreaming, the different life situations and needs of men and women have to be considered from the beginning and continuously reviewed in every project and program. The resulting findings are used to improve gender equality aspects in personnel recruitment and throughout the whole period of employment of women. The compatibility of leisure time, family and job has a high priority for both female and male staff. To be an attractive employer the Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft has to offer every employee the possibility to organize their work in flexible terms. The part-time working schemes and teleworking models already offered by the Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft as well as the little-used possibility of sabbaticals will be consequently extended.

Many Fraunhofer Institutes offer special work experience opportunities and open days to encourage more young women to take up an interest in technical subjects and thus widen their range of possible career choices. The "Girls' Day" project, sponsored by two German ministries, has become a permanent institution within the Fraunhofer Institutes since the year 2002.

The female doctorate program contributes to the promotion of future scientists within the scope of equal opportunity policies. The Executive Board of the Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft introduced this program in 1999 to motivate and reward Fraunhofer Institutes to engage more female junior employees. The selection criteria are the quota of female scientists, equal opportunity policies in the institutes and faculties (preference given to faculties in which women are under-represented, such as physics, electrical engineering and mechanical

engineering). A seminar on “career planning for junior women scientists” was elaborated for the participants to help them with the planning of their future career.

Like other organizations, the Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft employs mentoring programs as a means of helping women to make progress in their careers. Each junior candidate is supervised by an experienced manager. Some mentoring programs allow students to take an inside look at the world of research, others are designed as internal programs.

Another important part of the Fraunhofer equal opportunities policy is the implementation of the Gender Equity Law: The application of this law and the appointment of a gender representative are intended to avoid discrimination in recruitment activities. Furthermore, these regulations aim at a better compatibility of family and job.

More and more Fraunhofer Institutes now provide childcare facilities to help staff balance the demands of family and job. The Fraunhofer Institute centers in Stuttgart and Birlinghoven, the Fraunhofer Institute for Integrated Circuits IIS, the institutes in Karlsruhe and the Fraunhofer headquarters all provide nursery and crèche facilities.

TESORO:

This organization has no specific plans related to gender issues, but they follow gender equality criteria as part of their company philosophy.

4 Action plan

As a result of the analysis of the current situation in the consortium regarding gender aspects, a Gender action plan has to be implemented. The consortium will base this plan in the “Gender Toolkit” (FP7 funded project) and in the “Practical Guide to Improving Gender Equality in Research Organisations” released by Science Europe (Science Europe Working Group on Gender and Diversity).

According to this last document, the underlying causes of the gender imbalance at decision-making levels across all sectors are numerous and complex. However, it may be beneficial to highlight the following:

- Childbearing and caregiving are major determining factors for women leaving competitive research careers, but not the only factors; the lack of appropriate mentoring is also frequently cited and as such gender imbalance appears to be self-reinforcing.
- The working environment in Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) is often perceived as unsupportive of women candidates at all levels of seniority.
- One of the sharpest declines in the percentages of women in the traditional academic research career track occurs between the graduate and tenure track or permanent position career points. This is the so-called ‘leaky pipeline’

Management policies related to research grants, as enforced by national and international research funding agencies, can have a direct and indirect effect on facilitating the flexibility

and support required at critical career times for women researchers, such as, but not limited to, times associated with birth and caregiving.

The HISTO-MRI consortium will focus its efforts in the following issues:

- Monitor and document gender progress at all organisational levels of the project on an annual basis.
- Gender equality presentations at consortium meetings, training selection bodies and researchers in gender awareness to avoid gender biases.
- Promote the active participation of women in the consortium meetings.
- Promote the active participation of women in dissemination activities: publications, conferences and exhibitions, etc.
- Provide recommendations to avoid gender biases in the recruitment process, using the existing guidelines in some partners (CSIC, Fraunhofer).
- Encourage the enrolment in the project of young women researchers at early career stages (PhD, postdoc).
- Promote opportunities for part-time working and teleworking.
- Offer flexible working hours conditions, so that family conciliation is more feasible.
- Provide special support to women researchers during pregnancy and breastfeeding, and facilitate their update after maternity leave.
- Reconcile work and private life:
 - Project events will be organized so that travelling does not interfere with weekends
 - Minimize travelling, through adequate use of teleconferencing
 - Offer childcare on an individual basis at workshops and annual meetings